

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF EMIL RESLER IN THE STUDY OF KARABAKH ARCHEOLOGY

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the contribution of Emil Roesler, a German archaeologist, to the study of the archaeological sites of Nagorno-Karabakh. Roesler was one of the first researchers who began systematic excavations in this region at the end of the 19th century. His works played a key role in understanding the ancient civilizations that existed in the territory of Karabakh and its surroundings, and contributed to an in-depth study of cultural and historical ties between the South Caucasus and other regions of Eurasia. The article analyzes the results of the excavations conducted by Roesler, among which special attention is paid to the mounds dating back to the Bronze Age. These findings confirm the existence of close cultural and ethnic ties between local peoples and the broader Eurasian steppe civilizations. Roesler discovered many burial mounds and burial structures that contained objects made of precious metals, testifying to the high level of craft of the ancient peoples of this region. Among his significant discoveries are mounds demonstrating the peculiarities of the Northern (Scythian) culture, which indicates complex migration processes and cultural exchange in ancient times. The article also highlights the problem of illegal export of archaeological artifacts during the Armenian occupation and topical issues of the return of historical values. It is particularly noted that the works of Roesler and his followers laid the foundation for further research into the archaeology of Karabakh, despite the fact that his methodology differed significantly from modern standards. Nevertheless, his work remains an important source of information for subsequent generations of archaeologists.

Keywords: Archaeological research, burial mounds, Bronze Age, precious metals

Introduction. Archaeological research in Karabakh, which began at the end of the XIX century, laid the foundation for the study of the ancient history and culture of Azerbaijan. This area, rich in historical and archaeological monuments, gave unique information about various stages of the Bronze Age and other periods of development of the region.

The first references to the archaeological monuments of Karabakh date back to the 30s of the XIX century, when foreign travelers and researchers began to record ancient finds. However, a systematic study began with the work of the German scientist Emil Resler, who conducted a series of excavations in the region between 1891 and 1898. His research covered a wide range of geography and made significant contributions to the understanding of local archaeology.

Main part: In the 90s of the XIX century, Emil Resler was one of the pioneers of Karabakh archeology and visited the first Bronze Age monuments involved in research, including Khachinchay mounds. Working without official permission, but under the auspices of the St. Petersburg archaeological Commission, E. Resler conducted a series of excavations, the results of which are presented in the form of reports. These reports have become an important source of information about the mounds of Nagorno-Karabakh, their structure, burial practices and material culture.

Resler has recorded and excavated many monuments including Dashalti, Chanakhchi, Mehtikend, Gulabli, Zayshanli, Sirkhavandi, Damgulu, Khojaly, Shusha, Shushakandi, Gushchulu and Khachinchay.

Research carried out in Zerti, Sangar and Kettitapa mounds expanded the understanding of the Bronze Age in Azerbaijan and gave interesting results [8]. One of E. Resler's remarkable achievements was the discovery of the burial mounds, which date back to the 12th-11th centuries BC, with wooden constructions in the grave pit, burial of horses together, and traces of fire, revealing interesting features of the Northern (Scythian) culture [2].

These findings support the hypothesis of dense settlements between the peoples of Nagorno-Karabakh and the cultures of the northern steppes, emphasized in the work of M. N. Pogrebova.

Resler not only discovered many mounds and carried out excavation work, but also collected a significant number of artifacts and sent them to Germany for further study. Among them were both objects made of precious metals and other valuable finds indicating a high level of craftsmanship of the ancient inhabitants of this region. These materials fell into the hands of the famous anthropologist Rudolf Virkhov, which helped to deepen the knowledge of the ancient history of Karabakh [10].

The materials sent by Resler to Germany and studied by Rudolf Virkhov also contributed to the development of Anthropology and archeology, allowing to deepen the understanding of the ethnogenesis of the peoples of the South Caucasus.

The impact of the Northern culture on the Karabakh mounds mentioned by M. N. Zirzamova emphasizes the multidimensionality of cultural interactions in the region.

Despite the fact that the methodology of E. Resler was far from the modern standards of archaeological excavations, his works made it possible to collect a wide range of material cultural samples. These findings were published in the annual reports of the Russian Imperial Archaeological Commission and in German collections of archaeology, ethnography and anthropology[6].

E. Resler's work and further study of his findings confirmed a close relationship between the cultures of the South Caucasus and the wider territory of Eurasia. However, despite the international recognition of all archaeological finds in the territory of Azerbaijan as the property of the state, there is a problem of illegal export of artifacts, especially during the occupation of Armenian separatists[9].

The practice of "black archaeology" and archaeological looting has unfortunately led to the loss of many valuable artifacts, the history and origins of which could provide the key to understanding the ancient history of the region.

Despite the difficulties associated with the return of these finds, the importance of their preservation for the cultural heritage of Azerbaijan is undeniable.

With his research, Resler opened a new page in the archeology of Nagorno-Karabakh, demonstrating the richness and diversity of its ancient culture. He emphasized the importance of Kurgan graves, which are an important part of the Turkic cultural tradition, and contributed to deepening the understanding of cultural and historical ties between the peoples of the South Caucasus and neighboring regions.

Conclusion: Emil Roesler's work in Nagorno-Karabakh laid an important foundation for further research into the Bronze Age and other historical periods of the region. Despite the fact that his reports are mostly descriptive and do not contain precise chronological or cultural attributions, they have become a significant source of information for subsequent generations of researchers. His discoveries made an important contribution to the study of the archaeological sites of the South Caucasus and allowed to shed light on the cultural ties between the various civilizations of this territory. Over the past decades, archaeological research in Karabakh has significantly expanded our understanding of the ancient history of the region, leading to a number of significant discoveries. Among these finds, traces of early settlements, ancient burial mounds and unique artifacts occupy a special place, testifying to the high level of development of local cultures in the Bronze and Early Iron Ages. These discoveries highlight the important role of Karabakh as a cultural and economic center, through which numerous cultural and trade routes passed. Archaeological research has confirmed that for thousands of years Karabakh has been a meeting place for various cultures and civilizations. Being a kind of bridge between the ancient East and Europe, this region facilitated the exchange of technologies, ideas and goods. The multilayered cultural influence is reflected in archaeological excavations, which continue to provide new knowledge about the ancient world. Despite significant achievements in the study of the archeology of Karabakh, scientists face numerous challenges. One

of the key issues remains the need for an integrated approach to the analysis and interpretation of archaeological data using modern methods and technologies. It is also important to preserve the archaeological sites of the region, many of which are under threat due to economic development and social changes. The archaeologists of Karabakh face an important task — to continue studying and preserving the rich cultural heritage of the region. These efforts will not only allow a deeper understanding of the ancient history of Karabakh, but also strengthen intercultural dialogue and mutual understanding, which are so important in the modern world.

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